

An Analysis of Supply Chain Management: Crafting a Plan for Supply Chain and Inventory Management

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Abstract- This study examines supply chain and inventory management practices at IHI Incorporated, a company specializing in turbocharger supply and repair. Using a descriptive and correlational research method, data was collected from 51 respondents selected through purposive sampling. The findings revealed that most employees are male, around 35 years old, with college degrees, and 3-5 years of experience in rank-and-file positions. The assessment of supply chain management highlighted the importance of accurate demand forecasting, product diversification, and efficient distribution channels. Similarly, inventory management was emphasized for cost-effective operations, stressing the need to minimize inventory levels while maintaining adequate safety stocks. Statistical analysis showed a highly significant relationship ($r = 0.9999$) between supply chain management and inventory operations, indicating their close interdependence. Recommendations for improvement include regular assessments, enhanced inventory tracking systems, interdepartmental collaboration, training initiatives, and fostering a culture of continuous improvement. This study sheds light on supply chain and inventory dynamics at IHI Incorporated, offering actionable insights for enhancing operational efficiency and achieving organizational objectives.

Keywords- Supply Chain Management, Inventory Management, Demand, Products.

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's highly competitive business world shaped by globalization, consumer awareness, and technological advancements, it's crucial for companies to continuously promote their services to retain customers who have many alternatives. If any part of the supply chain, including contract manufacturers, storage facilities, or testing labs, experiences delays, it affects everyone involved. To mitigate such risks, businesses should communicate regularly with suppliers to address issues promptly and minimize financial losses.

Inventory management is often overlooked but plays a vital role in ensuring smooth operations. Supply chain managers need to have expertise in

inventory management to avoid issues like overstocking, which can lead to waste and financial losses. Effective inventory control helps companies meet customer demands while reducing costs. However, managing inventory levels can be challenging, as having too much inventory can lead to losses, while insufficient inventory disrupts production.

Therefore, this study focuses on evaluating the inventory and supply chain issues at IHI Incorporated, a company specializing in turbocharger supply and repair for ocean vessels and power plants. By addressing these issues, the company aims to enhance its production capacity and overall performance, ultimately increasing revenue and ensuring customer satisfaction.

1. Need of the Study

The study is needed to comprehensively assess and understand the state of supply chain and inventory management within IHI Incorporated. It aims to address various aspects, including the demographic profile of employees in terms of age, gender, education, position, and tenure, providing insights into the workforce composition. Additionally, the research endeavors to evaluate the assessment of supply chain management concerning demand, product handling, distribution, and logistics, aiming to gauge the effectiveness of current practices. Moreover, it seeks to assess inventory management in terms of accuracy, cost-efficiency, and quantity control, crucial for optimizing operational performance. Furthermore, the study aims to ascertain the perceived relationship between supply chain and inventory operations within the company. Finally, it aims to propose potential inventory plans that could enhance the overall supply chain and inventory management of IHI Incorporated, thereby addressing any identified shortcomings and optimizing operational efficiency.

2. Statement of the Problem

The research aims to explore the Supply Chain and Inventory Management practices within IHI Incorporated. Specifically, it seeks to address the following questions:

- What is the demographic profile of employees in terms of age, gender, highest educational attainment, position, and years in service?
- How is supply chain management assessed in terms of demand, products, distribution, and logistics?
- How is inventory management evaluated in terms of accuracy, cost, and quantity?
- Is there a significant relationship perceived by respondents between supply chain management and inventory operation at IHI Incorporated?
- What inventory plan could be implemented to enhance the company's supply chain and inventory management practices? These questions guide the study in understanding the company's operational dynamics and identifying potential areas for improvement.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

1. Assessment of Supply Chain Management

Considering the supply chain is crucial for a competitive benefit for the company's operations. The management of supply chain study focuses on how to improve resource utilization and deployment across the entire business to raise the organization's total value. An interconnected system of value-adding processes between the clients and vendors of an organization. The fundamental idea of receiving input from the company's suppliers, adding value, and ultimately delivering to the customers are the goals of supply chain activities. Any efficient supply chain operation must include collaboration and coordination. Every time there are gaps or breakdowns in the cross-functional teams' communication process, it results in waste that could drive up expenses. For instance, a lapse in communication could result in an excess or shortfall of goods, which would leave customers unsatisfied or result in excessive inventory expenses. A successful supply chain operation depends on improving the connections between all of the teams participating in the process. Levi (2014).

Demand

Supply unpredictability is usually caused by problems with the production system and challenges with suppliers' quantity and/or timing. The impact of supply was studied by Grasso and Taylor (2015), due to timing concerns, notable variations in the lead time of acquired items, and an MRP the system's performance is unpredictable. They discovered that controlling lead time reduces costs. When protecting against supply/timing uncertainty, However, the safety stock has a far bigger influence. Buzacott and Shanthikumar (2016), furthered this research and concluded that the choice between safety stock and lead times is determined by the forecast of future required shipments: if the forecast is favorable, safety lead time is preferred; however, if forecast timing is unknown and only the mean demand can be predicted, either safety lead time or safety stock will suffice. Because of the many applications in the industry, many models have been presented that

merely include demand uncertainty. When the stochastic demand distribution is uncertain, however, "no analytical solutions to safety stock are presented." Zhang, Xu, & Zhang (2015). Kazan, Nagi, and Rump (2015) consider the production effects of uncertain demand manufacturing numbers and timetables.

According to Chang, C. T., & Chou, H. C. (2016), the buyer's demand for each period is deterministic in the coordination system, the supplier replenishes all buyers, and all participants agree to schedule replenishment to minimize total system costs. We use small lot sizing and frequent delivery rules (JIT philosophy) to convey inventory between suppliers and buyers to meet the coordination system's goal. Furthermore, the coordination system allows for buyer demand adjustments to suit real-world scenarios, particularly in high-tech companies. Furthermore, the suggested technique can achieve the ideal number of deliveries, shipping sites, and shipment quantities in each order for all participants in the coordination system using mechanisms for minimizing total relevant costs.

Following Minghui Xu (2017), dealing with the demand unpredictability in a one-supplier-one-retailer supply chain Demand fluctuation frequently causes actual production to differ from what was originally intended, resulting in a cost departure from the production plan. Assuming that market demand is nonlinearly sensitive to retail price, it demonstrates how to efficiently manage demand uncertainty in a supply chain, both for centralized decision-making systems and for decentralized decision-making systems with perfect coordination.

Products

Sameer Kumar (2015), stated that because there are so many variables in a supply chain, manufacturers must have protocols in place to prevent product recalls. In the case of a quality or safety concern, firms must have traceability capabilities or containment mechanisms for parts, goods, and procedures throughout the global supply chain. Consumer goods companies must consider not just the financial costs of a product recall, but also the loss of goodwill and consumer risk.

Distribution

Coughlan (2017), a distribution channel is characterized as a group of independent businesses engaged in the process of making a good or service accessible for use or consumption. By enhancing goods or services, a distribution channel seeks to close the gap between producers and customers. Kim and Frazier (2019). Typically, the primary players in a distribution channel are seen as manufacturers, middlemen (wholesalers, retailers, and specialized), and end users. Coughlan (2017). Given these definitions, it is difficult to pinpoint where the distribution channel truly begins because there may be a number of producers involved in the final products' manufacturing at various 14 Literature Review stages. Some of these producers are situated close to the source of the raw materials, while others are situated closer to the location of the users or ultimate consumers. When creating a distribution channel, two decisions are crucial: a tactical decision and a strategic one. While the latter dictates the intensity of the chosen structure and channel management rules, the former determines the number of tiers between supplier and consumer. Rangan and Jaikumar (2015). Different social, cultural, economic, and political trends make these choices more complicated. Ensign (2019). The distribution channel appears to have a different perspective from supply chain management "inside the chain".

Logistics

The idea of responsiveness seems simple at first. According to many academics, responsiveness refers to a manager's or an organization's capacity to alter a course of action in response to changing circumstances. Aaker & Mascarenhas (2012); Bahrami (2015); Bowersox & Daugherty (2015); Evans (2018); Matusik & Hill (2017). Additionally, responsiveness is described as "the ability to react purposefully and within an appropriate time scale to customer demand or changes in the marketplace, to bring about or maintain a competitive advantage" Holweg (2015). Although Holweg's description presents a general principle that can be applied to any organization, it does not directly address the viewpoint of the network of

businesses that make up the supply chain and how they interact with demands as a whole.

2. Assessment of Inventory Management

Essentially, Planning and organizing are key components of inventory management and material control. A store is necessary where to purchase materials, and how much to purchase. Inventory control's goal is to make sure a continuous inventory supply with the least amount of cost continuing operating expenses for the business. Management of inventories is essential to organizing the availability of materials for the ongoing process to run well. To achieve marketing requirements and consumer pleasure, it synchronizes the functions of production, storage, and distribution. The extent of inventory controlling the lead time for restocking is another aspect. Such as product replenishment, returns, and damaged products, as well as demand forecasting, inventory carrying costs, asset management, readily accessible physical inventory valuation, inventory demand projection, space visibility projecting future inventory prices, and quality management. When making decisions about inventory, management must consider various cost elements such as the cost of delivering inventory, the cost of maintaining inventory, and the expenses associated with having inadequate inventory. (Hugo, Badenhorst-Weiss, and Van Rooyen 2002). According to (Miller, 2010) To achieve an ideal inventory level, which is a continuous process as the business needs to change and respond to the external environment, these factors must be balanced.

Accuracy

According to Chuang & Olivia (2015); Drakaki & Tzionas (2019); Hachem (2016) one of the attributes of good inventory management is high inventory record accuracy, which means there are few differences between physical and virtual inventory. However, inaccurate inventory records seem to be a major issue in a variety of businesses, particularly in retail and manufacturing Dai (2016); Karim (2018); Rekik (2019).

Furthermore, Mohamad (2016), stated that Inventory management has a significant impact on

company profits and losses. Inventory management is effective and has a favorable impact on a company's financial performance Sunday & Joseph (2017). Inventory makes up a significant portion of the assets of most industrial organizations. As a result, inventory must be adequately managed, as having an ideal degree of working capital management can optimize a company's profit Prempeh & Amankona (2020).

According to Chuang & Oliva (2015); Okyay (2017), when the inventory record does not match the physical inventory, it is called inventory record inaccuracy. Inbound transactions, shelf operations, and outbound transactions are all examples of anomalies. The business must work with wrong information and make incorrect decisions as a result of these errors, which are frequently caused by shrinkage and transaction errors.

As stated in a book by Brooks, R. B., & Wilson, L. W. (2015), we know where and how much we have at every stage of the process because we retain accurate and thorough records of each transaction. Unfortunately, many businesses do not keep their inventory records up to date. When the correct information is needed for material decisions, production scheduling, marketing, and financing, the outcome is confusion. These businesses must either make choices based on shaky inventory records or conduct time-consuming physical inventory checks before proceeding. A company's inventory records must be accurate for a variety of reasons, the most basic of which is to generate appropriate management plans.

According to Tony Wild (2018), clients are more demanding as a result, wanting the right thing to be delivered on time, and competitive pressures don't allow for that additional bit of stockholding, record accuracy has been a focus of concern for many organizations. Businesses have been allowed to become considerably more productive if they are given the following: accurate information, improved communication, and system integration, yet many businesses fail on the initial claim. Any inventory inaccuracy directly affects these two crucial performance indicators, let alone long-term

survival, at the same time that inventory management is under pressure (in most organizations) to improve availability and store less inventory.

Cost

Every management mistake ends up in inventory, according to Michel Bergerac (2021), Units, regardless of their size, require inventories, and an enterprise without an inventory of vital materials can be highly costly. Large inventories, on the other hand, might be similarly costly due to associated capital, storage costs, and the cost of inactivity, among other factors. Maintaining an appropriate inventory level is critical for predictability, supply unreliability, price protection, demand fluctuations, quantity discounts, lowering ordering costs, maintaining efficient product flow, maintaining better customer relationships, and ensuring that, despite market scarcity, men and machines are used to their full potential, and lowering purchasing costs Zomerdijk and Vris (2015). Inventory management and control are critical for a business since stock mismanagement can result in a loss of revenue for a company's long-term viability (Sprague and Wacker, 2015). A surplus of inventory increases the possibility of damage, spoilage, and loss while taking up space and costing money. In this setting, the lean production approach pioneered by (Womack, 2015) has been related to lower stockpiles; yet, too little inventory might cause production operations to be disrupted, raising the chances of bad customer service. The stock has numerous costs that must be considered while determining inventory levels. Unit costs, ordering costs, carrying costs, and stock-out costs are among them Smith (2016). As a result, it is a requirement for businesses to embrace it as a way to strengthen their competitiveness through good inventory management methods Rajeev (2017). Proper inventory management necessitates a thorough examination of the costs of overstocking, ordering, running out of stock, and back-ordering. As Ross (2017) observed, The Economic Order Quantity (EOQ) model is a technique for figuring out the appropriate inventory level that takes inventory carrying costs, stock-out costs, and overall expenses into account. All of these factors

help figure out the right inventory levels to keep. According to Lazaridis & Dimitrios (2018), maintaining optimal inventory levels lowers the cost of potential business interruptions or losses due to product scarcity, lowers supply costs, and protects against price changes. As Mengue (2019), stated Supply chain collaboration is also said to be a driving force behind good inventory management because it provides members of the chain with up-to-date information and can save costs management costs if appropriately controlled.

Quantity

According to Tariq Sheakh (2018), the availability of unfinished goods and raw materials in an organization's inventory (work-in-progress), and finished goods it keeps on hand to meet its operating demands. It is a major investment and a possible source of waste that needs to be carefully managed. The definition of inventory for a firm is a store of goods stocked up in anticipation of upcoming demand. When the inventory level reaches the required level, an order can be placed to replenish the item. Inventory difficulties and business failure can result from factors like having too many or too few supplies on hand. If an essential inventory item for an organization runs out, production may be halted. The term "inventory management" refers to the total system for managing inventories. The inventory management method is more effective at figuring out the ideal inventory level and resolving issues like lead time and safety stock. Because inventory is a special asset, inventory management has developed to solve the growing problems faced by most business organizations.

Significance Relationship between Supply Chain Management and Inventory Management

According to Beaumont (2018), The supply chain is an integrated process with at least four levels: suppliers, producers, distributors, and customers. It starts with the transformation of raw materials and concludes with the delivery of the finished product to customers. Studies show that SCM is a more comprehensive approach to traditional material management, now considering the complete

planned and integrated approach to the supply chain and various levels of suppliers and customers. Numerous management techniques have been developed to make it easier to provide customers and other organizations with effective and efficient services for stakeholders as a result of the continuously rising demand for goods and services across a variety of economic sectors. Inventory management is increasingly viewed as a tool for achieving overall operational efficiency and making the best use of resources across industries. Akindipe (2014). For large enterprises, in particular, highly effective supply chain management and delivery systems have thus become essential to ensure the timely, effective, and high-quality delivery of goods and services.

Effective In the current environment, inventory management is seen as more of a requirement than just a fad market, where customer happiness and service have emerged as key factors for an organization to differentiate itself from the competition. Each business must maintain some level of inventory effectively managed because it represents financial resources. Increased operational costs are a crucial factor in stock management for discriminating businesses. Many businesses have utilized basic inventory control. Procedures or inventory management strategies to control inventory expenditures.

The initial step might be to establish a tracking system for different levels of inventory to ensure excellence, maximum effectiveness, and efficiency. Increased inventory levels expense stock-outs and inventory levels are essential measures for measuring inventory expenditures and overhead costs and the creation of strategies for proactive inventory management in every business. Kurano (2014); Achebo& Omoregie (2013). A smart inventory management strategy involves determining the company's inventory requirements. Seasonal supply should be limited to a minimum, and dormant or reduce the slow-moving inventory. In general, managers should choose different stock levels to avoid overstocking or under stocking materials.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

1. Methodology

The researchers employed a descriptive and correlational method of research, which proved to be well-suited for this study's objectives. Descriptive research is particularly effective for outlining the characteristics of a population or topic under examination without delving deeply into the reasons behind specific occurrences.

In this study, descriptive research was instrumental in gathering and analyzing data related to employees' demographic profiles, including employment status, position, gender, and age, as well as details about supply and inventory management tools used within the company. This approach allowed the researchers to paint a comprehensive picture of the workforce and the systems in place for managing supplies, which was crucial for the study's development.

By incorporating correlational analysis, the researchers were able to identify potential relationships between different variables, providing valuable insights into the interplay between demographic factors and supply chain management effectiveness within the organization. The descriptive and correlational method facilitated the exploration and understanding of key factors relevant to the study, contributing to the generation of meaningful statistical findings and ideas for further development.

2. Population and Sample

The researchers applied Purposive Sampling, a form of non-profitability sampling in which the researchers will select respondents based on the objective of their study.

The researchers will use purposive sampling for their respondents because all respondents of the survey are selected because they fit a particular profile.

Using this category, researchers make use of convenience sampling in which they do not have to involve all the employees of the population in the

selection process, as long as they can get enough for those who are available. This sampling technique gives the data needed to find the sample with a 5% margin of error. The researcher calculated the sample size using Slovin's formula. Based on the result, the sample size is 51 respondents out of the total population of 61.

3. Conceptual Framework

Variables of the study contain dependent and independent variables. The study used a pre-specified method for the selection. This section outlines the steps involved in conducting the study. The first part focuses on gathering information, including employee demographics and assessments of supply chain and inventory management.

This data provides the basis for the study's conceptual framework and helps in generating results. The second part describes the methods and procedures for analyzing data using statistical tools.

This step involves addressing issues related to supply chain and inventory management, ultimately contributing to achieving the study's objectives and the third part discusses the outcomes, which involve assessing how supply chain and inventory management impact the company's performance. These results are essential for the researcher's understanding and development of their paradigm.

Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between supply chain management and inventory operation of IHI Incorporated as perceived by the respondent.

IV. RESULT & DISCUSSION

1. Results of Descriptive Statics of Study Variables

Descriptive Statics

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	20	40%
Female	20	40%
LGBTQIA+	10	20%
Total	50	100

Table 1 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents in terms of their gender. It is shown from the table that most majority of the respondents are Male with 40% (20). There are 40% (20) female respondents while there are 20% (10) LGBTQIA+ respondents.

Table 2: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
25 yrs. old and below	7	14%
26-30 yrs. old	14	28%
31-35 yrs. old	14	28%
35 yrs. old and above	15	30%
Total	50	100

Table 2 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents in terms of their age. It is shown from the table that most of the respondents are above 35 years old with 30% (15). There are 28% (14) respondents are aged 26-30 years old, 28% (14) 31-35 years old and there are 14% (7) respondents are below 25 years old.

According to BBC News (2015), performance tends to increase with age. Consequently, aging may affect the job performance of certain individuals, particularly in high-pressure jobs where heavy demands are placed on workers. Job performance is the efficiency of job conduct in actual work environments. Warr (2014). While some studies

show that performance declines with age, others show that job performance is more steady even while work capacity appears to be declining with age. Salthouse & Maurer (2015).

Table 3: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Elementary	1	2%
High School	3	6%
College	46	92%
Total	50	100

Table 3 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents in terms of their highest educational attainment. It is shown that 92% (46) of respondents are college graduates and 6% (3) are high school graduates. There are 2% (1) of respondents graduated from elementary. The amount of education obtained is frequently used to gauge the level of skills present in the populace and the labor force. The availability of enough highly skilled workers is essential to the OECD countries' economies. Resulting from the technological advancements that have. Due to the changing demands of the global labor market, there is a considerable need for those with advanced or specialized skills. Vidal and Nossol (2016).

Table 4: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Employee Position

Employee Position	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Rank and file	35	70%
Supervisor	8	16%
Manager	7	14%
Total	50	100

Table 4 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents in terms of their employee position. It is shown from the table that the majority of the respondents are rank and file with 70% (35), 16% (8) being supervisors and there are 14% (7) of respondents are managers.

According to a growing body of research on the status, companies can boost employee productivity by assigning employees relative ranks based on their performance. both theoretical investigations. Besley and Ghatac (2018).

Table 5: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Numbers of years

Number of years working	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1 year	4	8%
2-4 years	20	40%
8 years above	26	52%
Total	50	100

Table 5 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents in terms of their number of years working in IHI Incorporated. It is shown that 52% (26) of respondents are working for 3-5 years in IHI Incorporated. There are 40% (20) of the respondents are working for 2-3 years and 8% (4) of respondents are working for below 1 year.

Table 6: Respondents' Assessment of Supply Chain Management in Terms of Demand

Demand	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Annual audit and assessment of supplier performance to help maintain the quality of its product offered.	3.35	Agree
Created research and studies to improve product development.	3.33	Agree
Increases options in customizing goods and services and offering incentives or additional product features.	3.23	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.31	Agree

The table shows the assessment of the respondents in supply chain management in terms of demand. It is shown that overall, the respondents agreed with the statements which describe their assessment of supply chain management with an overall weighted

mean average of 3.42. The highest results of the respondents agreed with all the statements "Study consumer trends, historical sales, and seasonality data to enhance a company's ability to meet the customer demand in the most efficient way." (3.45), "Diversify supply chain" (3.45), and "Visiting the current and future target markets to help formulate an action plan to determine the needed demand." (3.37) is the lowest. Mahya and Mafakheri (2020) supported the above statement, and agreed that if the resources are aligned with requirements, there will be less inventory and waste, which will increase the efficiency and resilience of manufacturing processes (and the related supply chains).

Table 7: Respondents' Assessment of Supply Chain Management in Terms of Products

Products	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Annual audit and assessment of supplier performance to help maintain the quality of its product offered.	3.35	Agree
Created research and studies to improve product development.	3.33	Agree
Increases options in customizing goods and services and offering incentives or additional product features.	3.23	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.31	Agree

Table 7 presents the assessment of supply chain management in terms of product. The highest result in the assessment of Products is the Annual audit and assessment of supplier performance to help maintain the quality of the product offered with a mean of 3.35, and the lowest result with a mean of 3.33 created for research and studies to improve product development and Increases options in customizing goods and services and offering incentives or additional product feature

The overall weighted mean of 3.31 was rendered in the survey. The aforementioned result was supported by the study (Heriansyah & Ikatrinasari, 2017) agreed by which states that ensuring value for your potential clients, as well as the demand and that your final products are of the greatest possible quality before releasing them to the market. By enhancing the interaction between contractors and suppliers through this partnership arrangement, changes in the schedule and volume of material procurement will not interfere with overall project completion targets.

Table 8: Respondents' Assessment of Supply Chain Management in Terms of Distribution

Distribution	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Choose and put into practice the best supply chain distribution strategy for the goods and services to the final consumers.	3.11	Agree
Set proper distribution channels.	3.23	Agree
Ensures that the selling products have sufficient stocks enough for distribution in a cost-effective method.	3.15	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.17	Agree

Table 8 shows the respondents' agreement toward the assessment of Distribution. It is shown that overall, the respondents agreed with the assessment of Distribution with an overall weighted mean of 3.17. The respondents agreed on setting proper distribution channels with a mean of 3.23 which makes it the highest result. They also agreed on ensuring that the selling products have sufficient stocks enough for distribution in a cost-effective method with a mean of 3.23, and they agreed on

choosing and putting into practice the best supply chain distribution strategy for the goods and services to the final consumer with a mean of 3.11 which makes it the lowest result. To support the above statements, the selection of appropriate distribution channels, which can greatly boost the company's profit, is one of the most crucial strategic decisions made by firms. The distribution channels should identify which of the existing channels is the best, and future adjustments should be mentioned (Mao & Yie 2019).

Table 9: Respondents' Assessment of Supply Chain Management in Terms of Logistics

Logistics	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Checking first the required date needed by the end-users to determine the right date to expedite the deliveries.	3.29	Agree
Understand the key metrics, core processes, and long-term goals of the supply chain in the dissemination of goods and services in meeting the agreed time of delivery.	3.23	Agree
Understanding the unit of metric to ensure that the goods/services needed to be distributed are on the proper supply chain channels.	3.15	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.30	Agree

Table 9 highlights the overall weighted mean of 3.30 which means IHI Incorporated must optimize its supply chain logistics to speed up order fulfillment and promptly distribute the item in the most dependable, cost-effective, and timely manner (Heriansyah & Ikatrinasari, 2017). The highest results were with a weighted mean of 3.29

where the employees agreed that checking first required data needed by the end-users to determine the right date to expedite the deliveries and with the mean of 3.29 employees also agreed that understanding the key metrics, core processes, and long-term goals of the supply chain in the dissemination of goods and services in meeting the agreed time of delivery, and Understanding the unit of metric ensures that the goods/services needed to be distributed are on the proper supply chain channels with a mean of 3.15 the lowest result in the table.

Table 10: Respondents' Assessment of Inventory Management in Terms of Accuracy

Accuracy	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Determine restocks lead times for every specified item.	3.33	Agree
Update the inventory record and provide a quarterly report to address the fast-moving items vs. slow-moving items.	3.35	Agree
Safety stocks are needed for buffering to avoid the unavailability of stocks.	3.21	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.28	Agree

A 3.26 overall weighted mean with its verbal interpretation as "Agree" is presented in the preceding table, this means that an accurate inventory record also allows IHI Incorporated to track sales patterns and distinguish between fast-moving and slow-moving products. This statement is supported by Brooks, R. B., & Wilson, L. W. (2015) A company's inventory records must be accurate for a variety of reasons, the most basic of which is to generate appropriate management plans. The highest results in the table with a mean of 3.92 of employees agreed on keeping a system records inventory for monitoring stocks and item specifications. The lowest results show that

employees agreed to Provide orientation, annual training, and seminar to update personal knowledge in keeping inventory and proper warehousing (3.13).

Table 11: Respondents' Assessment of Inventory Management in Terms of Cost

Cost	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Operations of materials requirements planning system where bills of materials are 100% accurate.	3.52	Agree
Provide program-based and manual inventory type of management system.	3.21	Agree
Locked-up price proposals for a specific period of time to be offered to clients for price security.	3.03	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.29	Agree

Looking at the table above, the survey yielded all Agree in each of the questions under the Cost. This resulted in a 3.29 overall weighted mean.

It is shown that the highest result shows that respondents agreed on the operations of the materials requirements planning system where bills of materials are 100% accurate with a mean of 3.52.

According to (D.R. Kiran, Production Planning and Control, 2019) minimizing inventory levels while keeping the raw ingredients and parts for your product available when you need them. This lowers the cost of stocking goods and guarantees that

your business always has what it needs on hand. Other statements also considered locked-up price proposals for a specific period of time to be offered to clients for price security with a mean of 3.03, the lowest result in the table.

Table 12: Respondents' Assessment of Inventory Management in Terms of Quantity

Quantity	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Determine restocks lead times for every specified item.	3.33	Agree
Update the inventory record and provide a quarterly report to address the fast-moving items vs. slow-moving items.	3.35	Agree
Safety stocks are needed for buffering to avoid the unavailability of stocks.	3.21	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.28	Agree

The table shows that the highest result shows that respondents agreed on updating the inventory record and providing a quarterly report to address the fast-moving items vs. slow-moving items with a mean of 3.35 and the other respondents also agreed on safety stocks are needed for buffering to avoid the unavailability of stocks with a mean of 3.21 which made it the lowest result in the table. As long as internal and production controls are in place, the business can meet client demand and maintain financial flexibility (Sheakh, 2018).

2. Testing Hypothesis

To test the significant relationship between supply chain management and inventory management of IHI Incorporated as perceived by the respondents, the hypothesis was tested using Pearson correlation coefficient r:

Table 13: Relationship between Supply Chain and Inventory Management

Relation ship	Degr ee of Free dom	Compu ted r	Critical Value	Decis ion 0.05 alpha	Interpretat ion
Supply chain manag ement	58	0.9999	0.2732	There is a signifi cant relatio nship betwe en the two variabl es	Significant
Invent ory Operat ion					

Table 13 shows the relationship between supply chain management and inventory. The computed correlation coefficient r shows 0.9999 higher than the 0.5 level of significance, which therefore suggested not to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, there was a significant relationship between supply chain management and inventory operation.

The Proposed Plan for the Study

Plan for Supply Chain and Inventory Management						
Goal: To increase the efficiency of the supply chain and maintain sufficient inventory visibility in IHI Incorporated by addressing the improvement of functional areas.						
Improve ment of Function al Areas	Situational Analysis	Objectiv es	ected Output	Suggested Activity	Time Fram e	Person Respon sible
Improve the demand planning of the company	Visiting the current trends and future markets is not given time and resources.	- achieving a balance between keeping enough inventory on hand to satisfy the client's demand while avoiding having excess.	Statistical Forecast Portfolio Management	- Data preparation - Initial projection - Utilizing market intelligence - Reconcile bottom-up projections with top-down financial and sales forecasts, taking into account sales objectives and financial data. - Finalize a forecast. -Real-time analytics based performance monitoring	18 to 24 months	Marketi ng depart ment, Representat iv es from purchas ing, supply chain, and the Finance team

V. CONCLUSION

The study shows that most people surveyed at IHI Incorporated are guys around 35 years old, who went to college and have worked there for 3 to 5 years in regular jobs. They think it's really important to check how the company manages its supply chain to make sure products move smoothly, demand is predicted accurately, and costs stay low while keeping quality high. They also believe keeping track of inventory well is crucial for getting things done right, like making sure costs are controlled and the right amount of stuff is kept in stock. The study found that how well the supply chain and inventory management work together is pretty important for things like predicting demand, sorting out deliveries, and saving money. So, based on what they learned, they made a plan to improve how supply chain management works in the company.

Recommendation

Based on the conclusion of the study, several recommendations can be made to enhance supply chain and inventory management practices at IHI Incorporated:

1. Implement Regular Supply Chain Assessments

Conduct periodic evaluations of supply chain processes to ensure smooth product flow, accurate demand forecasting, and cost-effective logistics. This will help identify any inefficiencies or bottlenecks in the supply chain that need addressing.

2. Enhance Inventory Management Techniques

Improve inventory tracking systems and practices to ensure accurate stock levels, minimize waste, and prevent overstocking or stock outs. Utilize technology solutions for real-time inventory monitoring and optimization.

3. Strengthen Interdepartmental Collaboration

Foster closer collaboration between supply chain and inventory management teams to streamline operations and improve coordination. This can include cross-training employees and implementing regular communication channels.

4. Invest in Training and Development

Provide ongoing training programs for employees involved in supply chain and inventory management to enhance their skills and knowledge. This can include workshops on supply chain optimization, inventory control techniques, and the use of relevant software tools.

5. Continuous Improvement Initiatives

Establish a culture of continuous improvement within the organization, encouraging employees to identify and implement innovative solutions to enhance supply chain and inventory management practices.

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